

WORLD LAND RESOURCES AND THEIR USE

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Abstract.

The article describes the world experience in the use of land resources, the level and problems of land use, and the hypotheses of land resources of world scientists. At the same time, the scientific basis of the new problems arising in the field of land resources and their use also took place in this article. The ideas we put forward are important in solving these problems.

INTRODUCTION

The total land fund of our planet is 14.9 billion hectares, which is 29% of our planet. 4.03 billion parts (27%) of it are forests, 2.85 billion parts (19%) are pastures, 2.32 billion parts (15.5%) are deserts of various types, 1.63 billion parts (11%) are glaciers, 0.72 billion parts (4.8%) of rivers, bushes and swamps, 0.7 billion parts (4.7%) of tundra and lesotundra, 0.45 billion parts (3%) of eroded, salinized and swampy areas, 0.3 billion part (2%) is occupied by urban and agricultural centers. Cultivated areas are 1.9 billion hectares, which is equal to 13 percent of the total land fund. Currently, the arable land per capita is 0.3 hectares, compared to 0.5 hectares a quarter of a century ago. The area of arable land per capita is 0.9 hectares in the friendly countries that left the previous union, and 1.1 hectares in Uzbekistan. This means that it is almost 4 times more than what the world shows.

METHODS

The systematic-structural approach based on objectivity, universality, concreteness, logical, and historical dialectical principles was used in the research. This makes it possible to see the concepts of land resources and land reserves as a whole system of human society.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In developed European countries and the USA, almost all of the land suitable for agriculture has been developed. In some regions of South America, Australia, Africa and Asia, there are reserves of land resources that can still be exploited.

Ensuring the growing need for food of the world's population has become one of the most complex issues of the present time. With the increase in the number of people, the issues of increasing the production of agricultural products and at the same time expanding the area of cities and villages, developing industrial communication and allocating additional land for other needs remain urgent. Experts from different countries are working on this issue with great effort.

According to Russian scientists N.N.Rozov and M.N.Stroganova (1979), in the future, the area of agricultural land on our planet can be expanded to 2.66 billion hectares due to more pastures and fewer forests. The products from this area provide food for 8-9 billion people. According to V. A. Vashanov and P. F. Loyko (1975), there are 750-820 million hectares of reserve land in the world, which can be used to increase agricultural land to 2.2 billion hectares. The main part of this reserve land (640-660 million) is located in developing countries, so half of it is in Latin America, for example, only 30 million hectares (20%) of the 240 million hectares of fertile land in Argentina are cultivated. Currently, the arable land of the Amazon basin, which has 10 million people, can provide food for 1 billion people. According to UN experts, between 1970 and 2000, 80 million hectares of new land were developed around the world, of which 56 million hectares belong to developed countries. The expansion of arable land has been particularly large in Latin America and Tropical Africa.

During the analysis, the issue of land use is highlighted as another situation, according to which there is an opportunity to expand the area of cultivated land. For example, according to UNEP, the development of new land will reach 3.2 billion hectares by the year 2025, while the arable land per capita will decrease by 2 percent in 1975. The reason for this is that with the increase in the population, many lands are eroded and become unusable, and part of the land is used for the development of cities and industrial communications. According to the hypothesis of the American expert Brown (1978), between 1975 and 2000, the urban population of the planet will increase by almost two times, it will exceed 3 billion, and accordingly, an additional 63 million hectares of land will be needed for urban development.

Under the influence of human economic activity, the quality of the soil deteriorates and its productivity is observed to be at a lower level. In the history of its development, the society has made nearly 2 billion hectares of land unusable. As a result of desertification and salinization alone, 6-7 million hectares of land on our planet are lost from agricultural use only due to the influence of water and wind. This situation rightfully worries experts. The reason is that according to the

characteristics of the soil, its area decreases thousands of times. For example, it takes 1400-1700 years to create 10 cm thick soil. Soil of such a thickness can be rendered unusable by water erosion in 20-30 years. Sometimes, only a single flood is enough for this process.

In general, the state of the soil depends on how we affect it. Man takes products from the soil in his farming activities and uses them. It takes away the organic matter grown in the soil and makes it useless. At the same time, he fertilizes the soil, uses crop rotation and other agrotechnical activities, and on this basis enriches the soil and restores the quality of its products. If such activities are not carried out on time, carrying out activities only for the benefit of this day, it is possible to cause erosion of the soil, to accelerate its unusability due to salinization and waterlogging.

Such bitter truths are also found in the agriculture of Uzbekistan. Currently, the total area of the Republic is 44.9 million hectares, of which 28.1 million hectares are cultivated. The irrigated areas are 4.2 million hectares. In the previous years, the development of old-age areas, the opening of new lands and the expansion of farming were in full swing in the Republic. During 1975-1985, 1 million hectares of new land was developed. This activity has even risen to the level of savantism and originated under the motto: "A great hunter hunts a lion, a great young man opens up the land." But this activity did not give the expected result. The reason is that there was not enough attention to farming agro-techniques, the technology of crop rotation was replaced by cotton monoculture. Maps have become worse than normal, land reclamation works have decreased. As a result, the soil is subject to various erosions, salinization and swamping are accelerated, and the use of river water in agriculture has increased. The Aral Sea has come to the brink of disaster, and the salty sand spreading from it has begun to spread to the soil of the surrounding areas. Thus, as a result of these mistakes, 90-95% of the territory of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Bukhorp and Syrdarya regions became saline. Only in Bukhorp region, 53 thousand hectares of 270 thousand hectares of irrigated land were eroded by wind. In the Fergana valley located in the foothills and in the Tashkent region, large areas were affected by water erosion. Currently, due to the improper use of land resources, the livestock industry of the Republic is suffering a lot of damage. Of the 22 million hectares used as pastures for livestock, 6 million hectares have been affected by wind erosion and 3 million hectares by water erosion.

CONCLUSION

In general, it should be noted that since 1991, the development of new land in the Republic has been stopped. In the following years, cotton alone was abandoned, grain, wheat and cotton are alternately planted, water efficient use activities are being developed, these activities will give good results in the future.

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